

netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society

Grant Agreement number: 727066

Key Research Questions

WP5_ D5.3 v1.2

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1 Introduction

The WYRED project (netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society) (García-Peñalvo, 2016b, 2017; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016) aims to provide a framework for research in which children and young people can express and explore their perspectives and interests in relation to digital society, but also a platform (Durán-Escudero, García-Peñalvo, & Therón-Sánchez, 2017; García-Peñalvo, 2016a; García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017) from which they can communicate their perspectives to other stakeholders effectively through innovative engagement processes (WYRED Consortium, 2017a, 2017b).

The dialogues primary focus was to give a range of stakeholders the opportunity to share their voice in relation to a range of topics and themes that interest and/or concern them. The most important stakeholders being our children and young people and giving them a voice to share their thoughts, fears and feelings in relation to the online world.

The dialogues engendered lively and energetic debate among young people – the themes presented by the facilitators were based on the Delphi questionnaire topics mainly – however other areas of interest outside the digital society were also discussed and raised as issues of priority. Some partners identified possible research questions/areas of foci under the prioritized themes.

Below is a summary of the potential areas identified through the dialogues from which to generate the research questions and a number of actual research questions.

2 List of suggestions for the research activities arising from the Dialogues by Partner

Boundaries

Prioritized Topics	Research Activity / Questions
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Group 1 aims to focus on issues around discipline and rules in education and their pertinence and relevance.• Group 2 is interested in self-image and particularly the constraints involved in the presentation of self. The notion that we are forced to pander to the expectations we perceive in was of particular importance.• Group 3 (new) is interested in intolerance	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Group 1 chose to focus on the ways in which dress rules and codes within the school environment can affect behavior/ learning.• Group 2 felt that the question they would explore had to do with the contrast between what we feel we should wear and what we might want to wear. (There is clear overlap between these two groups going forward though this has not been

<p>of other cultures. Trowbridge is the town with the largest Polish community per capita in the UK and their perception is that this causes a degree of tension which they wish to explore.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group 4 is interested in the jobs that are available for under 18's to engage in casual work and the safety and job security issues involved in this • Group 5 (new) is interested in the way that different aspects of the way the Internet works may affect our lives. 	<p>explicitly recognized yet)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group 3 wants to explore the nature of the intolerance and perhaps the depth of knowledge people actually have of Polish culture. • Group 4 wants to explore the casual jobs market in Trowbridge, and understand the factors that may limit the number of jobs available. • Group 5 is interested in looking the forthcoming Internet safety law that the government will be publishing and how it may affect their lives.
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USAL – Asynchronous online and face to face sessions

Prioritized Topics	Research Activity / Questions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender stereotypes and discrimination. • Cyber bullying/shaming. • Tolerance to different cultures/opinions. • Necessary changes in education. • Internet safety and privacy. • Gender stereotypes and discrimination. • Emotional education and Internet. • Causes of stress among young people. • Self-image and self-confidence. 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internet and social media risks. 	
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DOGA

Prioritized Topics	Research Activity / Questions
Exploration of the Delphi topics.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No generated questions to date.

EARLY YEARS

Prioritized Topics	Research Activity / Questions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-image and self-confidence. • Cyber bullying and shaming. • Internet safety and privacy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No generated questions to date.

TAU

Prioritized Topics	Research Activity / Questions
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Changes required in education – e.g., education oriented towards the future 2. Self-image and self-confidence 	<p>A. How can we direct the education in such a way that it helps our future?</p> <p>B. How do we get rid of the fixation of memorization (in learning), and instead of it to give something more connected to the present, including understanding and thinking?</p> <p>C. How can education for thinking be promoted?</p> <p>A. How does the environment affect self-image and self-confidence?</p> <p>B. Does the ideal of beauty in the media evolve towards a more realistic and diverse direction, or to the opposite direction?</p>

<p>3. Privacy and security on the Internet</p>	<p>C. Is society today oriented toward more self-acceptance than in the past?</p> <p>D. What are the limits of privacy and how do you define and protect them?</p> <p>A. What causes cyberbullying and what will lead to the eradication of this phenomenon? (In the discussion there was a view that hatred will always exist, and on the Internet such behavior is very easy, so it is very difficult to eradicate the phenomenon)</p>
<p>4. Cyberbullying and shaming on the Internet</p>	<p>B. How do you protect freedom of expression together with respect for others and their rights?</p> <p>C. How an artificial intelligence system can be developed, such that identifies problematic words and will not allow them to be typed and distributed on the Web?</p> <p>A. What causes intolerance? (in the family, society, etc.)</p> <p>A. How can one influence the mentality of youth and encourage tolerance?</p>
<p>5. Tolerance to different opinions and cultures</p>	<p>A. What types of distress do young girls and young boys experience?</p>
<p>6. Causes of distress among young people</p> <p>Related topics raised during the discussion on distress:</p> <p>Poverty, stress, social pressure, over-achievement, educational pressure, "We are over-burdened and I miss my youth", "We are at a sensitive age and it is to influence us". Also the issue of security</p>	<p>B. What are the special reasons for distress among young people (versus adults)?</p>

<p>concerns (specific to Israel) was raised.</p> <p>2. Most important issues:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The most important definitely is Education (emphasis: financial education, teachers' status). There was a consensus about the highest priority of the education issue. • Employment prospects. • Tolerance. • Gender. <p>3. Top importance: Education and changes in the education system</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tolerance, including gender discrimination. In fact, many topics on the list can be regarded as part of tolerance. • The issue of refugees is perceived as part of the tolerance issue. • Self-image – and related to this, self-definition. One participant said that this is the most important issue: “everything stems from this”. “You have to know who you are and how you perceive yourself”. • Role of parents, friends and peer groups. <p>Additional important issues suggested by the participants (not included in Delphi)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mental health. • Exam anxiety. • Pressure in learning (overload). • Environmental Awareness & Environmental Security. 	<p>Possible focal points and research questions related to Education</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Freedom of choice of learning topics/contents. Today there is no such freedom. Questions could be from what age and which topics. Or what are the criteria of choice (benefits for future employment? Or just pure interest or fun in learning?). • Impact of technologies on education. • Individual / personalized education; the freedom to choose what to learn. Education should be adapted to the person and not vice versa. • Some participants pointed out that there is a problem of conflicting messages conveyed by adults (including teachers): On one hand, they encourage us “to experience new things” as much as we can while we are young, on the other hand this and that are “forbidden” (e.g. drugs, alcohol). • Special spaces / means where YP can express themselves are lacking. For example, through art. There are YP who wish to express themselves and share their feelings and/or artistic talents with the world, but they don't have the adequate place or means. One participant mentioned the “Spoken Word” concept (performance art that is word based) as a very good idea that can be followed. The ability to express feeling e.g. through art is crucial in many
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality of relations with friends. • Metal health/wellbeing; Emotional issues. • Veganism. • Children and YP with special needs. • Security. • The attitude to LGTB community (it was mentioned that unfortunately some YP still use words like “homo” as a sort of curse or insult). Although this can be regarded as part of the Tolerance topic, the opinion of many is that LGTB deserves a special focus. • Religion and morality. • Sexual harassment. • Body Shaming and wrong body images: participants said that the issue is not just shaming in social media. It is a broader problem: “Body shaming”, or the societal pressure that forces you to adopt certain body images as desirable. • Animals’ abuse, cruelty to animals. <p>Issues prioritized from Delphi</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Education – 100% (19). 2. Employment prospects – 47% (9). 3. Tolerance to different cultures/opinions 26% (5). 4. Internet safety and privacy 21% (4). <p>Education and changes in the education system Most children think that in the future, innovative technologies will change the way they learn and teach. Technologies like virtual reality will change</p>	<p>cases of YP with distress, that don’t have access to the adequate means. Some of them are in risk of deterioration if this is not taken care of.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptation of the education concept to present reality. More “preparation for life”. More consideration of alternative educational challenges that YP use (like social networks) that are not part of the curriculum today. • Bad imitation models. YP tend to imitate persons who are not projecting positive values. <p>What will be the purpose (the goal) of education in this new reality?</p>
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the way of teaching as well as the way of learning. In addition, it is thought that learning based on memorization will disappear and will no longer be relevant.

Gender stereotypes / discrimination - Most children think that this is an important issue. At the same time, they believe that gender gaps will be narrowed in the future. The hope is to create a proper balance between genders and narrow the gaps. There are occupations that are labeled as more feminine (teaching, nurses) or masculine, and the salary is different accordingly.

Internet safety & privacy – All the children mentioned that this is a very important issue. They feel that this issue is at the forefront of the public discourse in all media channels: television, journalism, social networks, etc. They distinguish between data protection and privacy when talking about the importance. In their opinion, data protection is more important while privacy will not be important in the future. Most of them think that young people care less about keeping their privacy. But at the same time in the digital world in the future - the important issue will be data protection and personal security.

Integration of migrants/refugees in schools and in the society – Most of the children think that this is important issue. In their opinion, it is important to make the distinction between refugees who are temporarily present in the country in light of problems in the country they left and immigrants who are in prolonged periods and eventually become citizens of the state. However, in both cases it is important to integrate them into society and not to create closed communities, separated from society. It is important to integrate them into

What are the ways and means to be taken to reduce the gaps in the future?

Research question could be related to the ways and policy that ensure data secure on the net.

What will be the appropriate ways and frameworks for integrating immigrants and refugees in society

<p>4. Cyber-Bullying.</p> <p>5. Future Prospects.</p> <p>Group 2</p> <p>1. Waste of food.</p> <p>2. Media literacy.</p> <p>3. Maritime Pollution.</p> <p>4. Education</p> <p>5. Tolerance for other countries.</p>	<p>4. What are the strategies to deal with cyber-bullying? Where can help be obtained? Why do people bully someone? What are the legal aspects of bullying?</p> <p>5. What are the requirements for jobs today? What are the consequences of digitalization for jobs? What are the job prospects for students who do not finish formal education? How can apprenticeship be made more attractive? How can I take a good decision for my future occupation (e.g. job-counselling, coaching)? How can insecure job situations be dealt with?</p> <p>1. Find out basic data (What, how much, etc.) What can be done in general to reduce waste of food? What can be done at our school to reduce waste of food.</p> <p>2. How can we distinguish between fake news and facts? How can fake news be impeded? How do governments or other organizations influence the media?</p> <p>3. Research for types of pollution. What are the effects on small islands/animals/plants?</p> <p>4. Alternative approaches. How will/shall the school of tomorrow be like? Alternatives to school grades. What are the effects of education to social classes/to future?</p> <p>5. Where do which cultures come together? How is our culture changed by other cultures? How do conflicts arise and when do they turn into wars? "Live and let live".</p>
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<p>Group 3</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Live, like I want to live. 2) Mobbing. 3) Education. <p>Group 4</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Waste of food. 2) Stress. 3) Animal protection. 4) Human trafficking. 5) Reutilization of resources. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What does this mean for me? 2. What are the reasons for mobbing in my personal environment? 3. How can I find a job which interests me makes pleasure to me? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Find out basic data (What, how much, etc.) What can be done in general to reduce waste of food? What can be done at our school to reduce waste of food? 2. Research questions not yet available
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OXFAM

Prioritized Topics	Research Activity / Questions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tolerance to different cultures/opinions. • Integration of migrants/refugees in schools and society. • Internet safety and privacy. • Gender stereotypes and discrimination. • Self-image. • Causes of stress for young people. • Changes in education system. 	<p>The links between authority and quality of the education curricula (subordination to teachers) how does it influence the learning process of students?</p> <p>- To which extent does fear of the future in terms of finding a job influence how you live the present?</p> <p>- To which extent do schools (up to high school) influence your personal self-esteem and security?</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cyberbullying. • Role of families and friends. <p>Most relevant issues:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Education. - Self-image. - Causes of stress. 	
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YEU

Prioritized Topics	Research Activity / Questions
<p>Group 1</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1: Necessary changes in education. 2: Tolerance. 3: Employment. 4: Integration. 5: Role of parents. 6: Self-image. 7: Gender Stereotypes. 8: Internet safety. 9: Cyberbullying. 10: Media literacy. 11: Causes of stress. 12: Adults' misunderstanding. <p>Group 2</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1: Necessary changes in education. 2: Gender stereotypes. 	

<p>3: Role of parents.</p> <p>4: Integration.</p> <p>5: Tolerance.</p> <p>6: Self-Image.</p> <p>7: Employment.</p> <p>8: Adults' misunderstanding.</p> <p>9: Causes of stress.</p> <p>10: Internet safety.</p> <p>11: Cyberbullying.</p> <p>12: Media literacy.</p> <p>Group 3</p> <p>1: Necessary changes in education.</p> <p>2: Self-image.</p> <p>3: Gender discrimination.</p> <p>4.1: Causes of stress.</p> <p>4.2: Employment prospects.</p> <p>5: Media literacy.</p> <p>6: Internet safety.</p> <p>7: Role of parents.</p> <p>8: Tolerance towards other cultures/opinions.</p> <p>9: Adults' misunderstanding.</p> <p>10: Integration of migrants and refugees.</p> <p>11: Cyberbullying/shaming.</p>	
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Prioritized Topics	Research Activity / Questions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Populist politics. • Money and happiness. • Travelling. • Living a full and varied life. • Food – food miles, cooking and eating together- • Lowering legal age to vote. • Brexit impact. • General election. • Authentic feminism. • Refugee situation in UK. • Empathy through communication and understanding. • LGBT rights, same sex marriage. • Cannabis – positive and negative effects. • Making bad choices. • Role of parents. 	

3 Conclusion

The dialogues facilitated by the 9 WYRED partners provided the opportunities for C&YP to explore both the digital and physical worlds in which they live. The themes identified throughout the Delphi process provided the stimulus for the later conversations to begin and to grow. However there was room for a number of other issues and topics to be explored which were initiated by the C&YP themselves. A wide range of potential research areas were identified throughout this process by some of the partners and this will be explored further.

Not everyone got to the stage of generating research questions as a result of the dialogues and partners will

have to further engage their children and young people in focusing on potential research topics and questions. The social dialogue phase has provided a unique opportunity for a range of stakeholders and most importantly our C&YP to be fully engaged in process that will put them at the heart of research involving the online world which is part of their everyday lives.

The results from the Social Dialogues for each partner are listed above with some partners giving potential research questions aligned with the prioritized themes from Delphi.

Delphi Report Results

206 young people and 69 stakeholders from different countries took part in the 1st round, while 260 young people and 89 stakeholders participated in the 2nd round. The prioritization of issues was done by two methods: first, the importance of each issue was rated using a scale 1 to 5. Second, by selecting 4 most important issues and ordering them by importance.

The results from both rounds show that young people consistently attribute the highest importance to the issues of “self-image and self-confidence”, “tolerance to different cultures/opinions”, and “necessary changes in education”. One issue, mental wellbeing, which was added in the 2nd round (based on free-text additions submitted by young people in the 1st round), is also perceived as very important. It should be noted that the importance of this issue was also emphasized in some of the initial face-to-face social dialogues with young people carried out by the project team within WP5.

Interestingly, the opinions of stakeholders regarding the most important issues is in general rather similar to young people, except one noticeable difference: the stakeholders attribute much higher importance than young people to the issue of media literacy, namely the reliability of information on the internet and in social media. It is interesting to note that this observation has been confirmed by some of the initial face-to-face social dialogues with young people.

(Concluding Remarks: WYRED Delphi Study Results Report July 2017)

The research questions generated by the partners are grouped below by topic for ease of reference.

4 Global List of Potential Research Questions from Prioritized Topics from Delphi Results

Prioritized Topics from Delphi Results	Research Activity / Questions
	Global List

<p>1. Self-image and self-confidence</p>	<p>The contrast between what we feel we should wear and what we might want to wear.</p> <p>How does the environment affect self-image and self-confidence?</p> <p>Does the ideal of beauty in the media evolve towards a more realistic and diverse direction, or to the opposite direction?</p> <p>Is society today oriented toward more self-acceptance than in the past?</p> <p>To which extent do schools (up to high school) influence your personal self-esteem and security?</p> <p>To explore the nature of the intolerance and perhaps the depth of knowledge people actually have of <i>(Polish)</i> culture</p>
<p>2. Tolerance to different cultures/opinions</p>	<p>How can one influence the mentality of youth and encourage tolerance?</p> <p>What will be the appropriate ways and frameworks for integrating immigrants and refugees in society with an emphasis on the education system?</p> <p>Where do which cultures come together? How is our culture changed by other cultures? How do conflicts arise and when do they turn into wars? "Live and let live".</p> <p>The ways in which dress rules and codes within the school environment can affect behavior/ learning.</p>
<p>3. Necessary changes in education</p>	<p>How can we direct the education in such a way</p>

	<p>that it helps our future?</p> <p>How do we get rid of the fixation of memorization (in learning), and instead of it to give something more connected to the present, including understanding and thinking?</p> <p>How can education for thinking be promoted?</p> <p>Freedom of choice of learning topics/contents. Today there is no such freedom. Questions could be from what age and which topics. Or what are the criteria of choice (benefits for future employment? Or just pure interest or fun in learning?)</p> <p>Impact of technologies on education</p> <p>Individual / personalized education; the freedom to choose what to learn. Education should be adapted to the person and not vice versa.</p> <p>Some participants pointed out that there is a problem of conflicting messages conveyed by adults (including teachers): On one hand they encourage us “to experience new things” as much as we can while we are young, on the other hand this and that are “forbidden” (e.g. drugs, alcohol).</p> <p>Special spaces / means where YP can express themselves are lacking. For example, through art. There are YP who wish to express themselves and share their feelings and/or artistic talents with the world, but they don’t have the adequate place or means.</p> <p>Adaptation of the education concept to present reality. More “preparation for life”. More consideration of alternative educational challenges that YP use (like social networks) that</p>
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<p>4. Mental wellbeing</p>	<p>are not part of the curriculum today.</p> <p>What will be the purpose (the goal) of education in this new reality?</p> <p>Alternative approaches. How will/shall the school of tomorrow be like? Alternatives to school grades. What are the effects of education to social classes/to future?</p> <p>A. What types of distress do young girls and young boys experience?</p> <p>B. What are the special reasons for distress among young people (versus adults)?</p> <p>Special spaces / means where YP can express themselves are lacking. For example, through art. There are YP who wish to express themselves and share their feelings and/or artistic talents with the world, but they don't have the adequate place or means. One participant mentioned the "Spoken Word" concept (performance art that is word based) as a very good idea that can be followed. The ability to express feeling e.g. through art is crucial in many cases of YP with distress, that don't have access to the adequate means. Some of them are in risk of deterioration if this is not taken care of.</p> <p>How can we distinguish between fake news and facts? How can fake news be impeded? How do governments or other organizations influence the media?</p>
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<p>5 Media literacy, namely the reliability of information on the internet and in social media</p>	
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